

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

SUPPLEMENTARY TABLE S1

Number	TimeTree Reference ID	First Author	Article Title	Year	Taxonomic Order	Family	Molecular dating method	Tree Prior (If Specified)
Subset of 50 Randomly Selected Studies								
1	Klicka2001a	Klicka	A cytochrome-b perspective on Passerina bunting relationships	2001	Passeriformes	Cardinalidae	Simple enforced strict molecular clock	NA
2	19111935	Lee	Phylogenetic uncertainty and molecular clock calibrations: a case study of legless lizards (Pygopodidae, Gekkota).	2009	Squamata	Pygopodidae, Diplodactylidae, Gekkonidae, Carphodactylidae	Penalised likelihood rate smoothing (r8s)	NA
3	21401769	Strutzenberger	Temporal patterns of diversification in Andean Eois, a species-rich clade of moths (Lepidoptera, Geometridae).	2011	Lepidoptera	Geometridae	Bayesian inference (BEAST)	Not specified
4	20860811	Light	Evolutionary history of mammalian sucking lice (Phthiraptera: Anoplura).	2010	Psocodea	Echinophthiriidae, Haematopinidae, Hoplopleuridae, Linognathidae, Pedicinidae, Pediculidae, Polyplacidae, Haematomyzidae, Trichodectidae, Philopteridae	Bayesian inference (BEAST)	Yule
5	23379348	Fior	Spatiotemporal reconstruction of the Aquilegia rapid radiation through next-generation sequencing of rapidly evolving cpDNA regions.	2013	Ranunculales	Ranunculaceae	Bayesian inference (BEAST)	Yule

6	16109706	Cunha	Patterns of cladogenesis in the venomous marine gastropod genus <i>Conus</i> from the Cape Verde islands.	2005	Neogastropoda	Conidae	Bayesian inference (MULTIDIVTIME)	Dirichlet-distributed relative ages
7	26302949	Rodriguez	Molecular phylogeny of Pompilinae (Hymenoptera: Pompilidae): Evidence for rapid diversification and host shifts in spider wasps.	2016	Hymenoptera	Pompilidae	Bayesian inference (BEAST)	Not specified
8	Hennequin2010a	Hennequin	Phylogenetics and biogeography of <i>Nephrolepis</i> - a tale of old settlers and young tramps	2010	Polypodiales	Nephrolepidaceae, Tectariaceae, Lomariopsidaceae	Bayesian inference (BEAST)	Yule
9	Riddle1995a	Riddle	Molecular Biogeography in the Pocket Mice (<i>Perognathus</i> and <i>Chaetodipus</i>) and Grasshopper Mice (<i>Onychomys</i>): the Late Cenozoic Development of a North American Aridlands Rodent Guild	1995	Rodentia	Heteromyidae, Cricetidae	Simple enforced strict molecular clock	NA
10	23273581	Metallinou	Conquering the Sahara and Arabian deserts: systematics and biogeography of <i>Stenodactylus</i> geckos (Reptilia: Gekkonidae).	2012	Squamata	Gekkonidae, Phyllodactylidae, Sphaerodactylidae	Bayesian inference (BEAST)	Yule
11	23236369	Töpel	Past climate change and plant evolution in Western North America: a case study in Rosaceae.	2012	Rosales, Fabales,	Rosaceae, Fabaceae, Rhamanaceae	Bayesian inference (BEAST)	Yule
12	15772660	Switzer	Ancient co-speciation of simian foamy viruses and primates.	2005	Primates	Cercopithecidae, Hominidae, Atelidae	Penalised likelihood rate smoothing (r8s)	NA
13	20196815	Fernández-Mazuecos	Ecological rather than geographical isolation dominates Quaternary formation of Mediterranean <i>Cistus</i> species.	2010	Malvales	Cistaceae	Bayesian inference (BEAST)	birth-death
14	Klaus2013a	Klaus	Out of Borneo: Neogene diversification of Sundaic freshwater crabs (Crustacea: Brachyura: Gecarcinucidae: Parathelphusa)	2013	Decapoda	Gecarcinucidae	Bayesian inference (BEAST)	birth-death
15	Drovetski2003a	Drovetski	Plio-Pleistocene climatic oscillations, Holarctic biogeography and speciation in an avian subfamily	2003	Galliformes	Phasianidae	Simple enforced strict molecular clock	NA

16	Bruyns2011a	Bruyns	Age and diversity in Old World succulent species of Euphorbia (Euphorbiaceae)	2011	Malpighiales	Euphorbiaceae	Bayesian inference (MULTIDIVTIME)	Dirichlet-distributed relative ages
17	19558710	Yamada	Adaptive radiation of gobies in the interstitial habitats of gravel beaches accompanied by body elongation and excessive vertebral segmentation.	2009	Gobiiformes	Oxudercidae	Penalised likelihood rate smoothing (r8s)	NA
18	22166838	Fouquet	Molecular phylogeny and morphometric analyses reveal deep divergence between Amazonia and Atlantic Forest species of Dendrophryniscus.	2012	Anura	Bufoinae, Leptodactylidae	Bayesian inference (BEAST)	birth-death
19	25070971	de Bruyn	Borneo and Indochina are major evolutionary hotspots for Southeast Asian biodiversity.	2014	Sapindales, Alismatales, Cucurbitales, Lamiales, Ericales, Malpighiales, Diptera, Lepidoptera, Coleoptera, Araneae, Blattodea, Opiliones, Hymenoptera, Decapoda, Venerida, Caenogastropoda, Cypriniformes, Beloniformes, Anura, Squamata, Passeriformes, Coraciiformes, Galliformes, Eulipotyphla, Carnivora, Chiroptera, Proboscidea, Primates, Rodentia, Scandentia	Meliaceae, Araceae, Begoniaceae, Gesneriaceae, Ericaceae, Rafflesiaceae, Culicidae, Nymphalidae, Pieridae, Lycidae, Tetragnathidae, Blaberidae, Stylocellidae, Sycophaginae, Palaemonidae, Gecarcinucidae, Potamidae, Corbiculidae, Pachychilidae, Cyprinidae, Adrianichthyidae, Cobitidae, Dicroglossidae, Ranidae, Homalopsidae, Nectariniidae, Cettiidae, Alcedinidae, Turdidae, Dicaeidae, Muscicapidae, Campephagidae, Phylloscopidae, Pycnonotidae, Rhipiduridae,	Bayesian inference (BEAST)	Yule

						Megapodiidae, Zosteropidae, Pachycephalidae, Pycnonotidae, Soricidae, Canidae, Pteropidae, Elaphantidae, Hipposideridae, Cercopithecidae, Felidae, Viverridae, Muridae, Sciuridae, Tupaiaidae		
20	Grismer2015a	Grismer	Repeated evolution of sympatric, palaeoendemic species in closely related, co-distributed lineages of <i>Hemiphyllodactylus</i> Bleeker, 1860 (Squamata: Gekkonidae) across a sky-island archipelago in Peninsular Malaysia	2015	Squamata	Gekkonidae	Bayesian inference (BEAST)	Yule
21	Mansion2009a	Mansion	Origin of Mediterranean insular endemics in the Boraginales: integrative evidence from molecular dating and ancestral area reconstruction	2009	Boraginales	Boraginaceae	Bayesian inference (MULTIDIVTIME)	Dirichlet-distributed relative ages
22	Bryson2011a	Bryson Jr	Evolutionary drivers of phylogeographical diversity in the highlands of Mexico: a case study of the <i>Crotalus triseriatus</i> species group of montane rattlesnakes	2011	Squamata	Viperidae	Bayesian inference (BEAST)	Yule
23	18432552	Burbrink	The taming of the skew: estimating proper confidence intervals for divergence dates.	2008	Squamata, Rhynchocephalia	Scincidae, Sphenodontidae, Leptotyphlopidae, Xenopeltidae, Boidae, Pythonidae, Cylindrophiiidae, Typhlopidae, Acrochordidae, Pareidae, Viperidae, Colubridae, Xenodermidae	Penalised likelihood rate smoothing (r8s)	NA
24	26299211	Divakar	Evolution of complex symbiotic relationships in a morphologically derived family of lichen-forming fungi.	2015	Lecanorales	Parmeliaceae	Bayesian inference (BEAST)	Not specified

25	Talavera2013a	Talavera	Establishing criteria for higher-level classification using molecular data: the systematics of <i>Polyommatus</i> blue butterflies (Lepidoptera, Lycaenidae)	2013	Lepidoptera	Lycaenidae	Bayesian inference (BEAST)	Constant size coalescent
26	26199366	Rothfels	The evolutionary history of ferns inferred from 25 low-copy nuclear genes.	2015	Cyatheales, Polypodiales, Gleicheniales, Hymenophyllales, Marattiales, Ophioglossales, Osmundales, Psilotales, Salviniiales, Schizaeales, Ginkgoales, Ephedrales, Pinales, Ranunculales, Brassicales, Poales, Piperales	Dennstaedtiaceae, Hymenophyllaceae, Marattiaceae, Marattiidae, Ophioglossaceae, Osmundaceae, Psilotaceae, Pteridaceae, Zamiaceae, Ginkgoaceae, Ephedraceae, Pinaceae, Polypodiaceae, Ranunculaceae, Brassicaceae, Poaceae, Piperaceae	Bayesian inference (MrBayes)	Uniform
27	Draisma2014a	Draisma	A re-assessment of the infra-generic classification of the genus <i>Caulerpa</i> (Caulerpaceae, Chlorophyta) inferred from a time-calibrated molecular phylogeny	2014	Bryopsidales, Dasycladales, Caryophyllales	Caulerpaceae, Udoteaceae, Cactaceae, Halimedaceae	Bayesian inference (BEAST)	Yule
28	17419074	Fain	Phylogeny of "core Gruiformes" (Aves: Grues) and resolution of the Limpkin-Sungrebe problem.	2007	Galliformes, Anseriformes, Charadriiformes, Ciconiiformes, Gruiformes	Rallidae, Heliornithidae, Psophiidae, Aramidae, Gruidae, Ciconiidae, Ardeidae, Charadriidae, Jacanidae, Alcidae, Recurvirostridae, Anseranatidae, Odontophoridae	Bayesian inference (MULTIDIVTIME)	Dirichlet-distributed relative ages
29	Cibois2004a	Cibois	Biogeography of eastern Polynesian monarchs (<i>Pomarea</i>): an endemic genus close to extinction	2004	Passeriformes	Monarchidae	Bayesian inference (MULTIDIVTIME)	Dirichlet-distributed relative ages
30	20525339	Datzmann	Evolution of nectarivory in phyllostomid bats (<i>Phyllostomidae</i> Gray, 1825, Chiroptera: Mammalia).	2010	Chiroptera	Phyllostomidae	Bayesian inference (BEAST)	Not specified

31	Nagy2004a	Nagy	Molecular systematics of racers\, whipsnakes and relatives (Reptilia : Colubridae) using mitochondrial and nuclear markers	2004	Reptilia	Colubridae	Simple enforced strict molecular clock	NA
32	25115033	Fabre	Rodents of the Caribbean: origin and diversification of hutias unravelled by next-generation museomics.	2014	Rodentia	Echimyidae, Chinchillidae	Not specified	Not specified
33	21655955	Wang	The complete mitochondrial genome sequences of <i>Chelodina rugosa</i> and <i>Chelus fimbriata</i> (Pleurodira: Chelidae); implications of a common absence of initiation sites (O(L)) in pleurodiran turtles.	2012	Crocodylia, Testudines	Trionychidae, Pelomedousidae, Chelidae, Geoemydidae, Chelydridae, Emydidae, Cheloniidae, Testudinidae, Platysternidae, Alligatoridae	Bayesian inference (BEAST)	Not specified
34	20587049	Liu	Rampant historical mitochondrial genome introgression between two species of green pond frogs, <i>Pelophylax nigromaculatus</i> and <i>P. plancyi</i> .	2010	Anura	Ranidae	Bayesian inference (BEAST)	Yule
35	20817110	Plazzi	Towards a molecular phylogeny of Mollusks: bivalves' early evolution as revealed by mitochondrial genes.	2010	Pholadomyoidea, Chamida, Myida, Veneroidea, Unionida, Nuculoida, Arcida, Limida, Ostreoida, Pteriida	Cuspidariidae, Pandoridae, Thraciidae, Astartidae, Mactridae, Pharidae, Tridacnidae, Myidae, Carditidae, Veneridae, Unionidae, Nuculanidae, Nuculidae, Arcidae, Limidae, Ostreidae, Anomiidae, Pectinidae, Pinnidae	Penalised likelihood rate smoothing (r8s)	NA
36	20530131	Biffin	Did Kauri (<i>Agathis</i> : Araucariaceae) really survive the Oligocene drowning of New Zealand?	2010	Pinales	Taxaceae, Sciadopityaceae, Podocarpaceae, Pinaceae, Cupressaceae, Araucariaceae	Bayesian inference (BEAST)	Yule

37	16112884	Zerega	Biogeography and divergence times in the mulberry family (Moraceae).	2005	Rosales	Moraceae	Bayesian inference (MULTIDIVTIME)	Dirichlet-distributed relative ages
38	20637292	Müller	Palaeo island-affinities revisited--biogeography and systematics of the Indo-Pacific genus <i>Cethosia</i> Fabricius (Lepidoptera: Nymphalidae).	2010	Lepidoptera	Nymphal+G91:G96idae	Bayesian inference (BEAST)	Yule
39	19573225	Su	Evolutionary divergence times in the Annonaceae: evidence of a late Miocene origin of <i>Pseuduvaria</i> in Sundaland with subsequent diversification in New Guinea.	2009	Magnoliales	Annonaceae	Bayesian inference (BEAST)	Yule
40	21951675	Rutschmann	Parallel ecological diversification in Antarctic notothenioid fishes as evidence for adaptive radiation.	2011	Perciformes	Bovichtidae, Pseudaphritidae, Eleginopidae, Nototheniidae, Artedidraconidae, Bathydraconidae, Channichthyidae	Bayesian inference (BEAST)	birth-death
41	21551126	Unmack	A phylogenetic analysis of pygmy perches (Teleostei: Percichthyidae) with an assessment of the major historical influences on aquatic biogeography in southern Australia.	2011	Perciformes	Percichthyidae	Bayesian inference (BEAST)	birth-death
42	31445202	Fua	Plastid phylogenomics and biogeographic analysis support a trans-Tethyan origin and rapid early radiation of Cornales in the Mid-Cretaceous.	2019	Cornales	Hydraneaceae, Loasaceae, Cornaceae, Alangiaceae, Nyssaceae, Davidiaceae, Mastixiaceae, Curtisiaceae, Grubbiaceae, Hydrostachyaceae	Bayesian inference (BEAST)	birth-death
43	26863936	Silva	Transcontinental dispersal, ecological opportunity and origins of an adaptive radiation in the Neotropical catfish genus <i>Hypostomus</i> (Siluriformes: Loricariidae).	2016	Siluriformes	Loricariidae	Bayesian inference (BEAST)	birth-death

44	Setoguchi2014a	Setoguchi	Sexual dimorphism and courtship behavior in <i>Drosophila prolongata</i>	2014	Diptera	Drosophilidae	Simple enforced strict molecular clock	NA
45	21749736	Castalanelli	Molecular phylogeny supports the paraphyletic nature of the genus <i>Trogoderma</i> (Coleoptera: Dermestidae) collected in the Australasian ecozone.	2012	Coleoptera	Dermestidae	Bayesian inference (BEAST)	Not specified
46	Vargas2013a	Vargas	Testing the biogeographical congruence of palaeofloras using molecular phylogenetics: snapdragons and the Madrean-Tethyan flora	2013	Lamiales	Plantaginaceae, Bignoniaceae, Acanthaceae, Orobanchaceae, Lamiaceae, Verbenaceae, Pedaliaceae, Scrophulariaceae, Gesneriaceae, Calceolariaceae, Oleaceae, Plocospermataceae	Bayesian inference (BEAST)	birth-death
47	15522810	Pitra	Evolution and phylogeny of old world deer.	2004	Artiodactyla	Cervidae, Moschidae	Non-parametric rate smoothing (TreeEdit)	NA
48	18775768	Reis	An old bilbo-like non-LTR retroelement insertion provides insight into the relationship of species of the virilis group.	2008	Diptera	Drosophilidae	Bayesian inference (MULTIDIVTIME)	Dirichlet-distributed relative ages
49	Richardson2001a	Richardson	Phylogenetic analysis of <i>Phyllica</i> L. (Rhamnaceae) with an emphasis on island species: evidence from plastid trnL-F and nuclear internal transcribed spacer (ribosomal) DNA sequences	2001	Rosales	Rhamnaceae	Non-parametric rate smoothing (TreeEdit)	NA

50	Toon2010a	Toon	Gondwanan radiation of the Southern Hemisphere crayfishes (Decapoda: Parastacidae): evidence from fossils and molecules	2010	Decapoda	Parastacidae	Bayesian inference (MULTIDIVTIME)	Dirichlet-distributed relative ages
First 50 Included Studies in the Dataset								
1	12554442	Hormiga	Speciation on a conveyor belt: Sequential colonization of the Hawaiian islands by Orsonwelles spiders (Araneae, Linyphiidae)	2003	Araneae	Linyphiidae	Non-parametric rate smoothing (TreeEdit)	NA
2	12565035	Vicario	Xantusiid "night" lizards: a puzzling phylogenetic problem revisited using likelihood-based Bayesian methods on mtDNA sequences.	2003	Squamata	Xantusiidae	Simple enforced strict molecular clock	NA
3	12572610	Penzo	Messinian salinity crisis and the origin of freshwater lifestyle in western Mediterranean gobies.	1998	Gobiiformes	Gobiidae	Simple enforced strict molecular clock	NA
4	12595609	Mercer	The effects of Cenozoic global change on squirrel phylogeny.	2003	Rodentia	Sciuridae	Simple enforced strict molecular clock	NA
5	12644400	Adkins	Higher-level systematics of rodents and divergence time estimates based on two congruent nuclear genes.	2003	Lagomorpha, Primates, Dermoptera, Rodentia, Scandentia	Hominidae, Atelidae, Cebidae, Galagidae, Lemuridae, Tupaiidae, Cynocephalidae, Ochotonidae, Leporidae, Ctenodactylidae, Pedetidae, Gliridae, Geomyidae, Dipodidae, Murinae, Gerbillinae, Sigmodontinae, Arvicolinae, Cricetinae, Thryonomyidae, Bathyergoidae, Hystricoidae, Octodontoidea, Erethizontoidea, Chinchilloidea, Caviodae	Penalised likelihood rate smoothing (r8s)	NA

6	12644563	Glazko	Estimation of divergence times for major lineages of primate species.	2003	Primates, Artiodactyla, Muridae	Hominidae, Bos, Mus, Rattus, Callitrichidae, Cebidae, Lorisidae	Simple enforced strict molecular clock	NA
7	12750466	Brady	Evolution of the army ant syndrome: the origin and long-term evolutionary stasis of a complex of behavioral and reproductive adaptations.	2003	Hymenoptera	Formicidae	Bayesian inference (MULTIDIVTIME)	Dirichlet-distributed relative ages
8	12759476	Saez	Pseudo-cryptic speciation in coccolithophores.	2003	Calcidiscaceae, Zygodiscales, Coccolithales	Calcidiscus, Helicosphaera, Umbilicosphaera, Pleurochrysis, Coccolithus	Simple enforced strict molecular clock	NA
9	12766228	Wildman	Implications of natural selection in shaping 99.4% nonsynonymous DNA identity between humans and chimpanzees: enlarging genus Homo.	2003	Primates, Rodentia	Cercopithecidae, Hominidae, Mus	Simple enforced strict molecular clock	NA
10	12777524	Lee	Molecular phylogenies and divergence times of sea urchin species of Strongylocentrotidae, Echinoidea.	2003	Echinoidea	Strongylocentrotidae	Simple enforced strict molecular clock	NA
11	12781743	Otsuka	Advanced formulation of base pair changes in the stem regions of ribosomal RNAs; its application to mitochondrial rRNAs for resolving the phylogeny of animals.	2003	<i>Not specified below phylum</i>	<i>Not specified below phylum</i>	Simple enforced strict molecular clock	NA
12	12801472	Williams	A molecular phylogeny of the Littorininae (Gastropoda: Littorinidae): unequal evolutionary rates, morphological parallelism, and biogeography of the Southern Ocean.	2003	Littorinimorpha	Littorinidae	Penalised likelihood rate smoothing (r8s)	NA
13	12821774	Douady	The Sahara as a vicariant agent, and the role of Miocene climatic events, in the diversification of the mammalian order Macroscelidea (elephant shrews).	2003	Macroscelidea	Macroscelididae	Bayesian inference (DIVTIME)	Dirichlet-distributed relative ages
14	12832653	Schrago	Timing the origin of New World monkeys.	2003	Primates	Cebidae, Hominidae, Cercopithecidae, Tarsiidae	Bayesian inference (MULTIDIVTIME)	Dirichlet-distributed relative ages
15	12878465	Douady	Molecular estimation of eulipotyphlan divergence times and the evolution of "Insectivora".	2003	Eulipotyphla, Afrosoricida	Erinaceidae, Soricidae, Talpidae, Tenrecidae, Potamogalidae	Bayesian inference (DIVTIME)	Dirichlet-distributed relative ages

16	12878467	Teeling	Nuclear gene sequences confirm an ancient link between New Zealand's short-tailed bat and South American noctilionoid bats.	2003	Chiroptera, Carnivora, Cetartiodactyla, Eulipotyphla, Perissodactyla, Pholidota	Mystacinidae, Talpidae, Manidae, Balaenopteridae, Bovidae, Felidae, Mormoopidae, Molossididae, Natalidae, Vespertilionidae, Phyllostomidae, Noctilionidae, Emballonuridae, Nycteridae, Megadermatidae, Hipposideridae, Rhinolophidae, Pteropodidae	Bayesian inference (DIVTIME)	Dirichlet- distributed relative ages
17	12899700	Averdam	Subunit sequences of the 4 x 6-mer hemocyanin from the golden orb-web spider, <i>Nephila inaurata</i> .	2003	Araneae	Araneidae	Simple enforced strict molecular clock	NA
18	12927134	Yuan	Monophyly and relationships of the tribe Exaceae (Gentianaceae) inferred from nuclear ribosomal and chloroplast DNA sequences.	2003	Gentianales	Gentianaceae	Non-parametric rate smoothing (TreeEdit)	NA
19	12940365	Near	Speciation in North American black basses, <i>Micropterus</i> (Actinopterygii: Centrarchidae).	2003	Perciformes	Centrarchidae	Penalised likelihood rate smoothing (r8s)	NA
20	12949132	Tamura	Temporal patterns of fruit fly (<i>Drosophila</i>) evolution revealed by mutation clocks.	2004	Diptera	Drosophilidae	Simple enforced strict molecular clock	NA
21	13678682_00490	Paton	RAG-1 sequences resolve phylogenetic relationships within Charadriiform birds.	2003	Charadriiformes, Turniciformes, Columbiformes, Galliformes, Gruiformes, Pterocliiformes	Burhinidae, Charadriidae, Pluvianellidae, Chionidae, Glareolidae, Haematopodidae, Jacanidae, Pedionomidae, Recurvirostridae, Rostratulidae, Scolopacidae, Thinocoridae, Stercorariidae, Alcidae, Laridae, Rynchopidae,	Penalised likelihood rate smoothing (r8s)	NA

						Sternidae, Pteroclididae, Gruidae, Phasianidae, Columbidae, Turnicidae		
22	13678682_00491	Paton	RAG-1 sequences resolve phylogenetic relationships within Charadriiform birds.	2003	Charadriiformes, Turniciformes, Columbiformes, Galliformes, Gruiformes, Pterocliiformes	Burhinidae, Charadriidae, Pluvianellidae, Chionidae, Glareolidae, Haematopodidae, Jacanidae, Pedionomidae, Recurvirostridae, Rostratulidae, Scolopacidae, Thinocoridae, Stercorariidae, Alcidae, Laridae, Rynchopidae, Sternidae, Pteroclididae, Gruidae, Phasianidae, Columbidae, Turnicidae	Penalised likelihood rate smoothing (r8s)	NA
23	13678682_00492	Paton	RAG-1 sequences resolve phylogenetic relationships within Charadriiform birds.	2003	Charadriiformes, Turniciformes, Columbiformes, Galliformes, Gruiformes, Pterocliiformes	Burhinidae, Charadriidae, Pluvianellidae, Chionidae, Glareolidae, Haematopodidae, Jacanidae, Pedionomidae, Recurvirostridae, Rostratulidae, Scolopacidae, Thinocoridae, Stercorariidae, Alcidae, Laridae, Rynchopidae, Sternidae, Pteroclididae, Gruidae, Phasianidae, Columbidae, Turnicidae	Penalised likelihood rate smoothing (r8s)	NA

24	13678682	Paton	RAG-1 sequences resolve phylogenetic relationships within Charadriiform birds.	2003	Charadriiformes, Turniciformes, Columbiformes, Galliformes, Gruiformes, Pterocliiformes	Burhinidae, Charadriidae, Pluvianellidae, Chionidae, Glareolidae, Haematopodidae, Jacanidae, Pedionomidae, Recurvirostridae, Rostratulidae, Scolopacidae, Thinocoridae, Stercorariidae, Alcidae, Laridae, Rynchopidae, Sternidae, Pteroclididae, Gruidae, Phasianidae, Columbidae, Turnicidae	Penalised likelihood rate smoothing (r8s)	NA
25	14530137	Yang	Comparison of likelihood and Bayesian methods for estimating divergence times using multiple gene Loci and calibration points, with application to a radiation of cute-looking mouse lemur species.	2003	Didelphimorphia, Perissodactyla, Artiodactyla, Carnivora, Primates	Didelphidae, Equidae, Rhinocerotidae, Physteridae, Balaenopteridae, Hippopotamidae, Bovidae, Ursidae, Felidae, Hominidae, Cercopithecidae, Callitrichidae, Galagidae, Lorisidae, Daubentoniidae, Lepilemuridae, Indriidae, Lemuridae, Cheirogaleidae	Bayesian inference (MULTIDIVTIME)	Dirichlet-distributed relative ages

26	14532706	Hasegawa	Time scale of eutherian evolution estimated without assuming a constant rate of molecular evolution.	2003	Primates, Lagomorpha, Rodentia, Carnivora, Perissodactyla, Artiodactyla, Eulipotyphla, Chiroptera, Proboscidea, Tubulidentata, Cingulata, Diprotodontia, Didelphimorphia, Monotremata, Sirenia, Hyracoidea	Hominidae, Hylobatidae, Leporidae, Gliridae, Sciuridae, Caviidae, Muridae, Phocidae, Canidae, Felidae, Equidae, Rhinocerotidae, Camelidae, Suidae, Bovidae, Hippopotamidae, Balaenopteridae, Physeteridae, Soricidae, Talpidae, Vespertilionidae, Rhinolophidae, Pteropodidae, Phyllostomidae, Elephantidae, Orycteropodidae, Chlamyphoridae, Macropodidae, Didelphidae, Ornithorhynchidae, Manidae, Pholidota, Castoridae, Heteromyidae, Hystricidae, Heterocephalidae, Echimyidae, Dinomyidae, Lemuridae, Trichechidae, Procaviidae	Bayesian inference (DIVTIME)	Dirichlet-distributed relative ages
27	14635877	Hrbek	Closing of the Tethys Sea and the phylogeny of Eurasian killifishes (Cyprinodontiformes: Cyprinodontidae).	2003	Cyprinodontiformes	Cyprinodontidae, Valenciidae, Anablepidae	Simple enforced strict molecular clock	NA
28	14667332	Vences	Multiple overseas dispersal in amphibians.	2003	Anura	Mantellidae, Rhacophoridae, Ranidae	Penalised likelihood rate smoothing (r8s)	NA

29	14668115	Wiegmann	Time flies, a new molecular time-scale for brachyceran fly evolution without a clock.	2003	Diptera	Tipulidae, Anisopodidae, Stratiomyidae, Xylomyidae, Xylophagidae, Vermilleonidae, Rhagionidae, Pelecorhynchidae, Tabanidae, Nemestrinidae, Acroceridae, Bombyliidae, Asilidae, Apioceridae, Mydidae, Therevidae, Scenopinidae, Atelestidae, Empididae, Dolichopodidae, Platypozidae, Syrphidae, Muscidae, Drosophilidae	Bayesian inference (MULTIDIVTIME)	Dirichlet-distributed relative ages
30	14668116	Jennings	Systematics of the lizard family pygopodidae with implications for the diversification of Australian temperate biotas.	2003	Squamata	Pygopodidae, Diplodactylidae	Bayesian inference (MrBayes)	Not specified
31	14728785	Nagy	Multiple colonization of Madagascar and Socotra by colubrid snakes: evidence from nuclear and mitochondrial gene phylogenies.	2003	Squamata	Colubridae, Psammophiidae, Pseudoxyrhopiidae, Elapidae, Atractaspidae, Boidae, Viperidae, Boodontinae	Penalised likelihood rate smoothing (r8s)	NA
32	14731304	Pisani	The colonization of land by animals: molecular phylogeny and divergence times among arthropods.	2004	Phyllococida, Architaenioglossa, Lithobiomorpha, Decapoda, Anostraca, Anomopoda, Podocopida, Xiphosura, Araneae, Scorpiones	Nereididae, Ampullariidae, Lithobiidae, Portunidae, Artemiidae, Daphniidae, Cyprididae, Limulidae, Theraphosidae, Buthidae	Bayesian inference (MULTIDIVTIME)	Dirichlet-distributed relative ages

33	14739240	Harrison	Four new avian mitochondrial genomes help get to basic evolutionary questions in the late cretaceous.	2004	Squamata, Anseriformes, Galliformes, Passeriformes, Ciconiiformes, Sphenisciformes, Charadriiformes, Accipitriformes, Falconiformes, Strigiformes, Psittaciformes, Tinamiformes, Struthioniformes, Rheiformes, Apterygiformes, Casuariiformes, Crocodilia, Testudines	Scincidae, Iguanidae, Anseranatidae, Anatidae, Phasianidae, Viduidae, Corvidae, Eurylaimidae, Ciconiidae, Spheniscidae, Scolopacidae, Haematopodidae, Accipitridae, Falconidae, Strigidae, Strigopidae, Tinamidae, Struthionidae, Rheidae, Apterygidae, Casuariidae, Alligatoridae, Cheloniidae	Non-parametric rate smoothing (TreeEdit)	NA
34	14766971	Davies	Darwin's abominable mystery: Insights from a supertree of the angiosperms.	2004	Apiales, Brassicales, Cornales, Laurales, Santalales, Saxifragales, Caryophyllales, Liliales, Ericales, Commelinales, Myrtales, Alismatales, Asparagales, Dioscoreales, Saxifragales <i>Not all included orders are noted; some information is missing/limited to the level of classes</i>	<i>No information below the level of order</i>	Non-parametric rate smoothing (TreeEdit)	NA
35	14871365	Faulkes	Phylogeographical patterns of genetic divergence and speciation in African mole-rats (Family: Bathyergidae).	2004	Rodentia	Bathyergidae, Heterocephalidae, Thryonomyidae	Simple enforced strict molecular clock	NA

36	14963099	Yoon	A molecular timeline for the origin of photosynthetic eukaryotes.	2004	<p>Bangiales, Compsopogonales, Cyanidiales, Porphyridiales, Rhodochaetales, Palmariales, Pyrenomonadales, Isochrysidales, Pavlovaes, Chattonellales, Triceratiales, Ectocarpales, Thalassiosirales, Brassicales, Anthocerotales, Chaetosphaeridiales, Chlamydomadales, Chlorellales, Fabales, Marchantiales, Mesostigmatales, Pinales, Psilotales, Poales, Glaucocystales, Nostocales</p>	<p>Bangiaceae, Compsopogonaceae, Cyanidiaceae, Galdieriaceae, Stylonemataceae, Dixoniellaceae, Porphyridiaceae, Rhodellaceae, Stylonemataceae, Rhodochaetaceae, Gigartinaceae, Palmariceae, Chroomonadaceae, Geminigeraceae, Pyrenomonadaceae, Noelaerhabdaceae, Isochrysidaceae, Pavlovaceae, Chattonellaceae, Triceratiaceae, Acinetosporaceae, Skeletonemataceae, Brassicaceae, Anthocerotaceae, Chaetosphaeridiaceae, Chlamydomonadaceae, Chlorellaceae, Fabaceae, Marchantiaceae, Mesostigmataceae, Pinaceae, Psilotaceae, Poaceae, Poaceae, Glaucocystaceae, Nostocaceae</p>	Penalised likelihood rate smoothing (r8s)	NA
37	14965909	Sorenson	Clade-limited colonization in brood parasitic finches (<i>Vidua</i> spp.).	2004	Passeriformes	Estrildidae, Viduidae, Ploceidae	Penalised likelihood rate smoothing (r8s)	NA

38	15008398	Nilsson	Radiation of extant marsupials after the K/T boundary: evidence from complete mitochondrial genomes.	2003	Diprotodontia, Microbiotheria, Peramelemorphia, Paucituberculata, Didelphimorphia, Monotremata, Eulipotyphla, Rodentia, Lagomorpha, Cingulata, Tubulidentata, Eulipotyphla, Carnivora, Perissodactyla, Artiodactyla, Primates, Galliformes, Rheiformes, Passeriformes, Crocodilia, Squamata, Testudines	Macropodidae, Phalangeridae, Vombatidae, Microbiotheriidae, Peramelidae, Caenolestidae, Didelphidae, Ornithorhynchidae, Tachyglossidae, Erinaceidae, Muridae, Leporidae, Gliridae, Sciuridae, Chlamyphoridae, Orycteropodidae, Talpidae, Felidae, Canidae, Phocidae, Rhinocerotidae, Equidae, Bovidae, Balaenopteridae, Hominidae, Cercopithecidae, Phasianidae, Rheidae, Corvidae, Viduidae, Alligatoridae, Iguanidae, Cheloniidae	Penalised likelihood rate smoothing (r8s)	NA
39	15014159	Seo	Estimating absolute rates of synonymous and nonsynonymous nucleotide substitution in order to characterize natural selection and date species divergences.	2004	Primates, Rodentia	Hominidae, Hylobatidae, Cercopithecidae, Cebidae, Tarsiidae, Lorisidae, Indriidae, Lemuridae, Muridae	Bayesian inference	Dirichlet-distributed relative ages
40	15019611	Groombridge	Molecular phylogeny and morphological change in the <i>Psittacula</i> parakeets.	2004	Psittaciformes	Psittaculidae	Simple enforced strict molecular clock	NA
41	15022759	van Tuinen	Calibration of galliform molecular clocks using multiple fossils and genetic partitions.	2004	Galliformes, Anseriformes	Cracidae, Numididae, Phasianidae, Megapodiidae, Odontophoridae, Cracidae,	Simple enforced strict molecular clock	NA

42	15058303	Schneider	Ferns diversified in the shadow of angiosperms.	2004 Polypodiales, Cyatheaales, Equisetales, Gleicheniales, Lycopodiales, Hymenophyllales, Schizaeales, Salviniales, Osmundales, Pinales, Magnoliales, Laurales, Canellales, Piperales, Chloranthales, Nymphaeales, Amborellales, Gnetales	Pteridaceae, Aspleniaceae, Blechnaceae, Dryopteridaceae, Cyatheaceae, Davalliaceae, Dennstaedtiaceae, Dicksoniaceae, Equisetaceae, Gleicheniaceae, Vittariaceae, Lycopodiaceae, Hymenophyllaceae, Lindsaeaceae, Polypodiaceae, Schizaeaceae, Marsileaceae, Nephrolepidaceae, Oleandraceae, Onocleaceae, Osmundaceae, Pinaceae, Plagiogyriaceae, Pteridaceae, Salviniaceae, Thelypteridaceae, Woodsiaceae, Annonaceae, Degeneriaceae, Eupomatiaceae, Himantandraceae, Magnoliaceae, Myristicaceae, Atherospermataceae, Calycanthaceae, Gomortegaceae, Hernandiaceae, Lauraceae, Monimiaceae, Canellaceae, Winteraceae, Aristolochiaceae, Piperaceae, Saururaceae, Chloranthaceae, Nymphaeaceae, Amborellaceae,	Penalised likelihood rate smoothing (r8s)	NA
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						Podocarpaceae, Gnetaceae, Taxaceae, Pinaceae, Gingkoaceae, Ephedraceae		
43	15062787	Plana	Pleistocene and pre-Pleistocene Begonia speciation in Africa.	2004	Cucurbitales	Begoniaceae, Datiscaceae	Non-parametric rate smoothing (TreeEdit)	NA
44	15084738	Peterson	Estimating metazoan divergence times with a molecular clock.	2004	Nuculida, Polycladida, Leptothecata, Actiniaria, Clypeasteroidea, Cidaroida, Mytilida, Echinoida, Enteropneusta, Craspedida, Comatulida, Valvatida, Priapulimorphida, Canalipalpata, Odonata	Nuculidae, Stylochidae, Campanulariidae, Metridiidae, Mellitidae, Cidaridae, Mytilidae, Dendrasteridae, Strongylocentrotidae, Harrimaniidae, Salpingoecidae, Antedonidae, Asterinidae, Priapulidae, Ptychoderidae, Chaetopteridae, Coenagrionidae, Lestidae	Penalised likelihood rate smoothing (r8s)	NA
45	15085543	Poux	Primate phylogeny, evolutionary rate variations, and divergence times: a contribution from the nuclear gene IRBP.	2004	Primates	Lorisidae, Galagidae, Lemuridae, Cheirogaleidae, Indriidae, Daubentoniidae, Tarsiidae, Atelidae, Callitrichidae, Pitheciidae, Cebidae, Cercopithecidae, Hominidae	Simple enforced strict molecular clock	NA
46	15120408	Megens	Tempo of speciation in a butterfly genus from the Southeast Asian tropics, inferred from mitochondrial and nuclear DNA sequence data.	2004	Lepidoptera	Lycaenidae	Simple enforced strict molecular clock	NA

47	15177677	Arnason	Mitogenomic analyses provide new insights into cetacean origin and evolution.	2004	Artiodactyla, Perissodactyla,	Balaenidae, Neobalaenidae, Eschrichtiidae, Balaenopteridae, Physeteridae, Ziphiidae, Platanistidae, Iniidae, Delphinidae, Monodontidae, Bovidae, Cervidae, Suidae, Hippopotamidae, Equidae, Rhinocerotidae	Penalised likelihood rate smoothing (r8s)	NA
48	15186809	Klanten	Patterns of lineage diversification in the genus <i>Naso</i> (Acanthuridae).	2004	Acanthuriformes	Acanthuridae, Zanclidae	Penalised likelihood rate smoothing (r8s)	NA
49	15205049	Zakharov	Molecular phylogeny, historical biogeography, and divergence time estimates for swallowtail butterflies of the genus <i>Papilio</i> (Lepidoptera: Papilionidae).	2004	Lepidoptera	Papilionidae	Penalised likelihood rate smoothing (r8s)	NA
50	15288062	Balke	MtDNA phylogeny and biogeography of Copelatinae, a highly diverse group of tropical diving beetles (Dytiscidae).	2004	Coleoptera	Dytiscidae	Non-parametric rate smoothing (TreeEdit)	NA

SUPPLEMENTARY FILE S2

List of search terms for MEDLINE, EMBASE, Web of Science, and SCOPUS:

MEDLINE (232 Articles):

(phylog*[MeSH Terms]) AND ((tree propert*[Text Word]) OR (tree shape*[Text Word]) OR (tree balance[Text Word]) OR (phylogeny shape*[Text Word]) OR (topological propert*[Text Word]) OR (tree imbalance[Text Word]) OR (statistical propert*[Text Word]))

EMBASE (73 Articles):

phylog*.kw. and (tree shape or tree propert* or tree balance or phylog* shape or statistical propert* or tree imbalance or topological propert*).af.

Web of Science (446 Articles):

TS=(phylog*) AND (ALL=("tree shape") OR ALL=("tree propert*") OR ALL=("tree balance") OR ALL=("phylogeny shape") OR ALL=("topological propert*") OR ALL=("statistical propert*") OR ALL=("tree imbalance*"))

SCOPUS (246 Articles):

KEY (phylog*) AND ALL (tree AND shape OR tree AND propert* OR tree AND balance OR phylogeny AND shape OR topological AND propert* OR statistical AND propert* OR tree AND imbalance)

Supplementary Figure 2: Flowchart for articles included in the scoping review

SUPPLEMENTARY TABLE S3

Tree Shape and Branch-Length Indices for Binary Trees

Index	Description	Interpretation ^a	Software Availability in R	Source
(Im)balance Indices*				
Colless index, I_c	Sum of absolute differences subtended by left and right leaves of internal nodes, including the root; an aggregate imbalance value among internal nodes.	Lower values suggest greater balance.	apTreeshape (Bortolussi et al. 2006), castor (Louca and Doebeli 2018), phyloTop (Kendall et al. 2018), treebalance, (Mareike Fischer et al. 2021) treeCentrality (Chindelevitch 2019)	(Colless 1982)
Normalized Colless Index, I_c	Colless index normalized by the maximum value for a tree of that size.	Lower values suggest greater balance.	apTreeshape, castor, phyloTop, treebalance	(Heard 1992)
Colless-like indices, $\mathbb{C}_{D,f}$	Sum of the balance values of the internal nodes relative to f (f-size) and D (dissimilarity) of a tree. A generalization of the Colless index to rooted non-binary trees, with several variations.	Lower values suggest greater balance.	CollessLike (Mir et al. 2018), treebalance	(Mir et al. 2018)

Equal weights Colless index (I_2 index)	Modified Colless index that applies equal weight to all internal nodes of a tree; counteracts ‘deep’ nodes being weighted heavier in the standard I_c .	Lower values suggest greater balance.	treebalance	(Mooers and Heard 1997)
Total I (I') index	Sum of imbalance values of all binary nodes in the tree. Imbalance values are the “ratio between the observed deviation of the larger pending subtree from the minimum value possible and the maximum deviation possible” (Fischer et al. 2021).	Lower values suggest greater balance.	treebalance	(Fusco and Cronk 1995; Purvis et al. 2002)
Mean/Median I (I') index	Mean/median of imbalance values of all binary nodes in the tree, where imbalance values for I are defined as above.	Lower values suggest greater balance.	treebalance	(Fusco and Cronk 1995; Purvis et al. 2002)
Sackin index	Sum of the edges from a leaf to the root for all leaves; a sum of depths on tree T.	Lower values suggest greater balance.	apTreeshape, castor, phyloTop, treebalance, treeCentrality	(Sackin 1972; Kirpatrick and Slatkin 1993)
Normalized Sackin index	Sackin index divided by a normalization value.	Lower values suggest greater balance.	phyloTop	(Blum et al. 2006)
Total cophenetic index, Φ	Sum of the depths of the common ancestor of all pairs of leaves (i.e., sum of cophenetic values [depth of the most recent common ancestor]).	Lower values suggest greater balance.	CollessLike, TotalCopheneticIndex (Mir et al. 2013), TreeTools (Smith 2019), treebalance	(Mir et al. 2013)

B ₁ index	The sum of the inverse heights of subtrees subrooted to internal nodes of a tree, excluding the root.	Higher values suggest greater balance.	treebalance	(Shao and Sokal 1990)
B ₂ index	Measures the equitability of arriving at the leaves of a tree when starting at the root and assuming equiprobable branching at each inner vertex; it is a Shannon-Wiener information function (Fischer et al. 2021).	Higher values suggest greater balance.	treebalance	(Shao and Sokal 1990)
Average leaf depth (\bar{N})	Mean of leaf depths in a tree, where depth is the number of leaves in a pending subtree attached to each node.	Lower values suggest greater balance.	treebalance	(Sackin 1972; Shao and Sokal 1990)
Leaf Depth Variance (σ_N^2)	Variance of leaf depths in a tree.	Lower values suggest greater balance.	treebalance	(Sackin 1972; Shao and Sokal 1990; M. Coronado et al. 2020)
Colijn-Plazotta rank	Recursively defined bijective mapping between rooted binary trees and the positive integers.(Fischer et al. 2021)	Lower values suggest greater balance.	treetop, treebalance	(Colijn and Plazzotta 2018; Rosenberg 2021)
<i>J</i> index	Number of interior nodes that are not balanced in a rooted, binary tree.	Lower values suggest greater balance.	symmeTree (Kersting and Fischer 2021), treebalance	(Rogers 1996)
Symmetry nodes index (SNI)	Number of interior nodes which are not symmetry nodes; a node is a symmetry node if its two maximal pendant subtrees are isomorphic.	Lower values suggest greater balance.	symmeTree, treebalance	(Kersting and Fischer 2021)

Ŝ-shape statistic	Sum of the log value of all clade sizes (for all internal nodes) in a tree minus one.	Lower values suggest greater balance.	treebalance, apTreeShape, castor	(Blum and François 2006)
Maximum depth	Maximum depth of any leaf in the tree, where depth is the number of edges from a leaf to the root.	Lower values suggest greater balance.	phyloTop, treebalance	(Colijn and Gardy 2014)
Maximum width	Maximum number of nodes for each depth, d , in the tree.	Higher values suggest greater balance.	phyloTop, treebalance, treeCentrality	(Colijn and Gardy 2014)
Width-depth ratio	Ratio of the maximum width of a tree to the maximum depth.	Higher values suggest greater balance.		(Colijn and Gardy 2014)
Maximum difference in widths	Maximum difference in width values at any value for depth, d .	Higher values suggest greater balance.	phyloTop, treebalance	(Colijn and Gardy 2014)
Mean depth	Mean topological distance of each node, including both internal nodes and leaves, to the root.	Lower values suggest greater balance.	phyloTop, treeCentrality	(Herrada et al. 2011)
Rooted Quartet index	Balance index based on the symmetry of the evolutionary history of every set of 4 leaves; sum of symmetry values of each 4-tuple of leaves in a tree.	Higher values suggest greater balance.	treebalance	(Coronado et al. 2019)
Furnas rank	Ranking of trees, which occurs through the “left-light rooted ranking” system, which assigns an integer value rank to each tree with a given number of terminal nodes. Balanced trees receive larger values relative to the number of possible distinct	Higher values suggest greater balance.	treebalance	(Furnas 1984; Kirpatrick and Slatkin 1993)

	topologies.			
stairs/stairs1/ staircase-ness measure	The proportion of sub-trees for all vertices that are imbalanced (i.e., sub-trees where the left child contains more leaves than the right child, or vice-versa).	Lower values suggest greater balance.	treebalance, phyloTempo (Norström et al. 2012), phyloTop, treeCentrality	(Norström et al. 2012)
stairs2	The mean ratio between the number of leaves of the smaller and larger pending subtree over all inner vertices.(Fischer et al. 2021) The average of all the $\min(l,r)/\max(l,r)$ values of each sub-tree, where l and r are the number of leaves in the left and right children of a subtree.(Norström et al. 2012)	Higher values suggest greater balance.	treebalance, phyloTop, treeCentrality	(Norström et al. 2012)
Other Tree Indices				
Mean I'_{10} index	Mean $I(I')$ index for the 10 earliest nodes of a tree.			(Fusco and Cronk 1995; Purvis et al. 2002)
Number of cherries	Number of adjacent pairs of leaves with a common ancestor node.		phyloTop, ape (Paradis and Schliep 2019), treebalance, treeCentrality	(McKenzie and Steel 2000)
Normalized number of cherries	Number of cherries divided by half the number of tips in a tree.		phyloTop	(McKenzie and Steel 2000)
Modified cherry index	Number of leaves which are not in a cherry in a rooted, binary tree.			(Kersting and Fischer 2021)

Number of r -pronged nodes or r -caterpillars	Number of nodes which subtends r number of cherries, or the number of caterpillars with r number of leaves.			(Rosenberg 2006; Chindelevitch et al. 2021)
D index (weighted ℓ_1 distance)	Compares the empirical and theoretical distributions of the number of subtrees under a Yule model. Is the weighted ℓ_1 distance between the two distributions.			(Blum and François 2005)
Degree of root imbalance	The proportion of taxa found in the more diverse group (maximal pending subtree) compared to the total number of taxa from the root.			(Guyer and Slowinski 1993)
Area Per Pair (APP) index	The average distance between all pairs of leaves in a tree, where distance denotes the number of edges that connect leaves.		treebalance	(Lima et al. 2020)
IL Number	Number of internal nodes with a single tip child; equivalent to modified cherry index for rooted, binary trees.(Fischer et al. 2021)		phyloTop	(Colijn and Gardy 2014)
Ladder lengths	Maximum number of connected IL nodes with a single leaf descendant, divided by the total number of leaves.		phyloTop	(Colijn and Gardy 2014)
Average ladder length	Mean size of ladders in a tree.		phyloTop	(Colijn and Gardy 2014)
Maximum height	Maximum height of tips in the tree.		phyloTop, treeCentrality	(Metzig et al. 2019)
Maximum betweenness**	Maximum number of shortest paths that pass through a particular node.		treeCentrality	(Metzig et al. 2019)

Maximum closeness**	Sum of lengths of the shortest paths between one node and all other nodes (maximum thereof).		treeCentrality	(Metzig et al. 2019)
Average pathlength**	The average topological distance between any two nodes.		treeCentrality	(Metzig et al. 2019)
Diameter**	Longest possible path between two nodes in the tree.		treeCentrality	(Metzig et al. 2019)
Pitchforks	Number of substructures consisting of three tips.		phyloTop, treeCentrality	(Metzig et al. 2019)
Wiener index**	Sum of the lengths of the shortest paths between all pairs of nodes.		treeCentrality	(Metzig et al. 2019)
Number of clades with a specific size	The frequency of different clade sizes for all pending subtrees in a tree.		TreeTools, treeCentrality	(Rosenberg 2006)
Length of longest and shortest pendant edge	The length of the longest and shortest pendant edges in a tree, where a pendant edge is an edge incident with a tip.			(Steel and Mooers 2010; Bocharov et al. 2022)
Cumulative stemminess	The proportion of the total length of the edges of the subset (including the subtending edge, or "stem") that is accounted for by the length of the sub-tending edge of the subset.			(Fiala and Sokal 1985)
Non-cumulative stemminess	Similar to cumulative stemminess but does not give higher weights to groups nearer the tips of the tree.		***	(Rohlf et al. 1990)

^aThis can depend on the structure of the tree (i.e., the most balanced trees according to one index may not be the most balanced according to other indices). All indices consider caterpillar trees to be the least balanced, but the most balanced may differ (e.g., I_2 and B_1 versus rooted quartet index) (Fischer et al. 2021).

*As defined by (Fischer et al. 2021). Further derivations and details for the majority of indices can also be found within (Fischer et al. 2021).

**Centrality and general network measures, as defined by (Metzig et al. 2019).

***Coded in R by Smith et al. (Smith et al. 2021)

Some metrics can be normalized based on # of tips in the tree (e.g., IL number) or mean path length (e.g., Wiener index)

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SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURE S4

Supplementary Figure 4
Z-scores for Scenario 1 Indices; Dotted Lines Denote the Sample Mean

Z-score

SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURE S5

Supplementary Figure 5
Z-scores for Scenario 2 Indices; Dotted Lines Denote the Sample Mean

SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURE S6

Supplementary Figure 6

Z-scores for Scenario 3 Indices; Dotted Lines Denote the Sample Mean

SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURE S7

Supplementary Figure 7
Z-scores for Scenario 4 Indices; Dotted Lines Denote the Sample Mean

Z-score

SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURE S8

